

ACTION OF SODIUM ON ETHYL β -METHYLBUTANE- $\alpha\beta$ -TRICARBOXYLATE. PART II. STRUCTURE OF THE ETHYLATED CONDENSATION PRODUCT

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The product of the action of sodium on ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate on ethylation furnishes ethyl 3-methyl-5-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3 : 5-dicarboxylate, since on hydrolysis it affords β -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylic acid, m. p. 172-73°, which Baker was unable to obtain in a state of purity. The structure of the latter is rigidly proved by rational synthesis. An independent synthesis of the isomeric γ -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid, m. p. 169°, is also described.

In part I (Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1943, 20, 173) it has been shown that ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta$ -tricarboxylate on sodium condensation followed by methylation of the resulting sodio-salt gives ethyl 3 : 5-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-3 : 5-dicarboxylate (I, R = Me) as the sole product, apparently no trace of the isomeric ethyl 2 : 3-dimethylcyclopentan-1-one-2 : 3-dicarboxylate (II, R = Me) could be detected.

(I)

(II)

Baker (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 1548) was, however, unable to ethylate the above Dieckmann condensation product with sodium ethoxide and ethyl iodide in the usual way although this difficulty was overcome by the use of sodamide in dry ether and a large excess of ethyl iodide. The ethylated product was formulated as (II, R = Et) since on hydrolysis with alcoholic potash it gave γ -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, R₁ = H, R₂ = Et), m. p. 155°, the structure of which was not rigidly proved. In view of this discrepancy it seemed desirable to re-examine Baker's work in the light of the facts already ascertained.

(III)

In the first instance by carrying out the ethylation of the Dieckmann product *in situ* with ethyl iodide in the usual way, the difficulties which rendered the experiments of Baker so laborious have been entirely obviated. The ethylated ester gives no colouration with ferric chloride and on hydrolysis with alcoholic potash yields a tricarboxylic acid, m. p. 155°, along with a little gummy substance from which no crystalline product could be isolated. On repeated crystallisation from concentrated hydrochloric acid the tricarboxylic acid melts sharply at 172-73°. On hydrolysis with hydrochloric acid, on the other hand, the ethyl ester gives an acidic product consisting for the most part of a liquid keto-acid which apparently gives a homogeneous semicarbazone, m. p. 191°. Since Baker (*loc. cit.*) represented the tricarboxylic acid as γ -methyl-*n*-

hexane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid it seemed desirable to prepare a specimen of this acid, for direct comparison, by an unambiguous method.

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -methylbutane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (IV, $R_1=R_2=H$; Banerjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 18, 425) is ethylated with ethyl iodide and sodium ethoxide to give ethyl $\gamma\delta$ -dicyano- γ -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (IV, $R_1=H$; $R_2=Et$). The latter on hydrolysis with concentrated hydrochloric acid furnishes γ -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, $R_1=H$; $R_2=Et$), m. p. 169° . The latter proves to be quite different from the tricarboxylic acid, m. p. 173° , derived from the ethylated ester (see above) since they show a mutual depression of their melting points when mixed. The triethyl ester (as III, $R_1=H$; $R_2=Et$) is allowed to react with sodium and the resulting ethyl 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-3:5-dicarboxylate (V, $R_1=CO_2Et$; $R_2=X=Et$) is hydrolysed to give 2-ethyl-3-methylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic acid (V, $R_1=X=H$; $R_2=Et$) which is directly converted into the semicarbazone m. p. 213.14° . Evidently, therefore, the keto-acid (V, $R_1=X=H$; $R_2=Et$) must be different from the isomeric acid (V, $R_1=Et$; $R_2=X=H$) isolated from the ethylated ester.

It follows, therefore, that the crystalline tricarboxylic acid, m. p. 172.73° , must be correctly represented as β -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$). The latter has accordingly been synthesised by the process outlined in the following scheme. Ethyl α -ethyl-laevalate (VI) (Thorne, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1881, 39, 337; Young, *Annalen*, 1883, 216, 340) is condensed with ethyl cyanoacetate in presence of acetamide and acetic acid (*cf.* Cope, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 2329) to give ethyl α -cyano- β -methyl- Δ^4 -hexene- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (VII). The latter on treatment with hydrogen cyanide furnishes ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (IV, $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$) (*cf.* Hope and Sheldon, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2223; Lapworth and McRea, *ibid.*, p. 2752; also Bardhan and Ganguly, *ibid.*, 1936, 1852), which is smoothly hydrolysed to β -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$), m. p. 173° , alone or in admixture with the tricarboxylic acid obtained from the ethylated ester.

(VI)

(VII)

The corresponding triethyl ester (III, $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$) on treatment with sodium gives ethyl 3-methyl-5-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate (V, $R_1=X=Et$; $R_2=CO_2Et$). This on hydrolysis with dilute acid affords 3-methyl-5-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic acid (V, $R_1=Et$; $R_2=X=H$) as a liquid which is characterised by the preparation of a semicarbazone, m. p. 191° , identical in all essential respects with the semicarbazone of the keto-acid obtained from the ethylated ester.

Clearly, therefore, the tricarboxylic acid, m. p. 173° , derived from the ethylated ester must be represented as β -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$). Consequently the ethylated ester should be formulated as (I, $R=Et$). Since Baker's ethylated ester exhibits no colouration with ferric chloride, there can be no question that Dieckmann ester

(II, R=H) behaves in an abnormal manner in presence of sodamide and ethylates at the carbon atom marked (*) leading to the formation of the keto-ester (V, R₁=Et; R₂=CO₂Et; X=Et) which can of course afford β -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid (III, R₂=H; R₁=Et) on hydrolysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium Condensation of Ethyl β -Methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate and Ethylation of the Sodio-salt: Formation of Ethyl 3-Methyl-5-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3:5-dicarboxylate (I, R=Et).—Ethyl β -methylbutane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylate required for the purpose was prepared by a modification of Ruzicka's method (Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*). The triethyl ester (20.8 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 1 hour with finely divided sodium (1.03 g.) suspended in dry benzene (25 c.c.). The clear solution obtained was cooled in ice, treated with ethyl iodide (5 c.c.) and kept overnight. Next day, another 5 c.c. of ethyl iodide were added to it and it was refluxed for 24 hours. The product was treated with water, the benzene layer was separated, washed and the benzene distilled off under reduced pressure. The product distilled at 142°/6mm., yield 8.8g. It gave no colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 62.0; H, 8.0. C₁₄H₂₂O₅ requires C, 62.2; H, 8.1 per cent).

*Acid Hydrolysis of the Ethylated Product: Formation of β -Methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic Acid (III, R₁=Et; R₂=H)*—The above product (4 g.) was heated on a water-bath for 3 hours with potassium hydroxide (4 g.) in 25% aqueous alcoholic solution. The alcohol was then evaporated off with the addition of water. The alkaline solution was acidified, saturated with salt and extracted with ether, and the solid residue obtained on evaporation of the ether was crystallised several times from concentrated hydrochloric acid. The acid melted at 172-73° (mixed m. p. with an authentic specimen of β -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid). A mixture of this acid with pure γ -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic acid melted gradually from 148-58°. (Found: C, 51.4; H, 6.9. C₁₀H₁₆O₆ requires C, 51.7; H, 6.9 per cent).

Ketonic Hydrolysis of the Ethylated Product: Formation of 3-Methyl-5-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic Acid (V, R₁=Et; R₂=X=H).—The ethylated product (4 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 16 hours with 8% aqueous hydrochloric acid (40 c.c.). It was neutralised with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether to remove any neutral matter. The aqueous solution was then acidified, saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The liquid acid obtained on evaporation of the ether was converted into the semicarbazone. It crystallised in needle-shaped crystals and melted with decomposition at 191° after two crystallisations from methyl alcohol, (mixed melting point with an authentic sample of the semicarbazone of 3-methyl-5-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic acid). (Found: C, 52.5; H, 7.4. C₁₀H₁₁O₃N₂ requires C, 52.8; H, 7.5 per cent).

*Synthesis of γ -Methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\gamma\delta$ -tricarboxylic Acid (III, R₁=H; R₂=Et) and 3-Methyl-2-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic Acid (V, R₁=X=H; R₂=Et).*—Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -methylbutane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate required for the purpose was prepared according to Banerjee (*loc. cit.*).

*Ethyl $\gamma\delta$ -Dicyano- γ -methyl-*n*-hexane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (IV, R₁=H; R₂=Et).*—This was prepared by adding ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -methylbutane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (19.95 g.) to an ice-cold solution of sodium (1.72 g.) in absolute alcohol (28 c.c.). Ethyl iodide (10 c.c.) was then added to

it and it was kept overnight. The reaction was completed by refluxing on the water-bath for 24 hours. The product was diluted with water and the oily liquid separating was taken up in ether and distilled. The product was obtained as a colourless mobile liquid boiling at $175^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 17.5 g. (Found : C, 60.9 ; H, 7.4. $C_{18}H_{24}O_6N_2$ requires C, 61.2 ; H, 7.4 per cent).

γ-Methyl-α-hexane-α,β-tricarboxylic acid (III, $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Et$).—The above product (16 g.) was hydrolysed by heating on a sand-bath for 25 hours with 5 volumes of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The clear solution obtained was evaporated completely to dryness and extracted with ether. The residue obtained on evaporation of the ether was esterified by the alcohol-vapour method in the usual way. The product distilled at $150^{\circ}/5$ mm., yield 8g. (Found : C, 60.4 ; H, 8.7. $C_{14}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 60.7 ; H, 8.8 per cent).

The pure acid was obtained by hydrolysing the triethyl ester with excess of concentrated hydrochloric acid till a clear solution was obtained. It was then evaporated to dryness on the water-bath and the solid acid obtained was crystallised several times from concentrated hydrochloric acid. It melts at 169° . (Found : C, 51.4 ; H, 6.8. $C_{10}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 51.7 ; H, 6.9 per cent).

Ethyl 3-methyl-2-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3:5-dicarboxylate (V, $R_1 = CO_2Et$; $R_2 = X = Et$).—The above triethyl ester (3.6 g.) was heated on the water-bath with molecular sodium (0.37 g.) suspended in dry benzene (12 c.c.). The reaction started on heating and was complete in 1 hour. It was then treated with ice-water and acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated, washed well with water and the benzene evaporated. The residual oil on distillation gave ethyl 3-methyl-2-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3:5-dicarboxylate (2.45 g.), b. p. $150^{\circ}/8$ mm. It gave a deep violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 61.8 ; H, 8.1. $C_{14}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 62.2 ; H, 8.1 per cent).

3-Methyl-2-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic Acid (V, $R_1 = X = H$; $R_2 = Et$).—The keto-dicarboxylic ester (2.3 g.) was hydrolysed by heating on a sand-bath for 12 hours with 6 % aqueous hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.). It was then neutralised with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether to remove any neutral matter. The aqueous solution was then acidified, saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The crude keto-acid was obtained as a liquid on evaporation of the ether. The semicarbazone was readily obtained by treating the product in a little spirit with a concentrated aqueous solution of semicarbazide acetate. It crystallises from dilute methyl alcohol as a microcrystalline powder, m. p. $213-14^{\circ}$ (decomp.). (Found : C, 52.7 ; H, 7.7. $C_{10}H_{14}O_6N_2$ requires C, 52.8 ; H, 7.5 per cent).

Pure 3-methyl-2-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic acid (V, $R_1 = X = H$; $R_2 = Et$) was obtained as a crystalline solid on hydrolysing the semicarbazone with dilute hydrochloric acid (1:2). The mixture was gently heated on the water-bath till a clear solution was obtained. The solution was then saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The solvent was then evaporated completely and the solid residue after drying on a porous plate was purified by crystallisation from petroleum ether containing a little benzene, m. p. 91° . (Found : C, 63.4 ; H, 8.2. $C_8H_{10}O_6$ requires C, 63.5 ; H, 8.2 per cent).

Synthesis of β-Methyl-α-hexane-α,β-tricarboxylic Acid (III, $R_1 = Et$; $R_2 = H$) and *3-Methyl-5-ethyl cyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic Acid* (V, $R_1 = Et$; $R_2 = X = H$).—Ethyl α-ethyl laevulate, was prepared after Thorne (*loc. cit.*), with some modifications by condensing the sodio-salt of ethyl acetoacetate with ethyl α-bromobutyrate. Hydrolysis of the product was effected with dilute hydrochloric acid (*cf.* also Young, *loc. cit.*) and α-ethyl laevulic acid, thus obtained, was esterified in presence of hydrogen chloride.

Ethyl acetoacetate (35.7 g.) was added drop by drop to an ice-cold suspension of finely divided sodium (6.32 g.) in benzene (70 c.c.) and then kept overnight. Next day, ethyl α -bromobutyrate (53.6 g.) was added to it and it was refluxed on the water-bath for 20 hours. It was then treated with water, the benzene layer was separated, washed and the benzene evaporated. The residual oil was then distilled in *vacuo*, b.p. 122°/6mm., yield 38.5 g.

Ethyl α -acetyl- β -ethylsuccinate, thus obtained, was heated on a sand-bath for 20 hours with 5 volumes of dilute hydrochloric acid (1:2). It was then evaporated completely on the water-bath. The dry liquid residue (17 g.) was heated on the water-bath for 10 hours with absolute alcohol (80 c.c.) and 8 c.c. of alcoholic hydrogen chloride (saturated at 0°). The alcohol was then distilled off and the product was taken up in ether, washed with dilute sodium carbonate solution and water and the ether evaporated. The residual liquid gave ethyl α -ethylsuccinate (16 g.), b. p. 88°/6mm.

Ethyl α -Cyano- β -methyl- Δ^4 -hexene- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (VII).—Ethyl α -ethylsuccinate (15.9 g.) was mixed with ethyl cyanoacetate (10.5 g.), acetamide (2 g.) and glacial acetic acid (35 c.c.). The acetic acid was distilled off slowly during 6 hours, so that the temperature of the vapour was between 105° and 115°. The product was taken up in ether, washed with water and the ether evaporated. The liquid remaining was then distilled in *vacuo*, when with the exception of some unchanged product below 100°/5mm., it boiled at 150°/5mm., yield 16 g. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 7.8. $C_{14}H_{21}O_4N$ requires C, 62.9; H, 7.8 per cent).

Ethyl $\alpha\beta$ -dicyano- β -methylhexane- $\alpha\delta$ -dicarboxylate (IV, $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$) was prepared by treating the above unsaturated cyano-ester (15.7 g.) in spirit (75 c.c.) with a solution of potassium cyanide (7.7 g.) in water (42 c.c.). It was cooled in ice-water and 20% hydrochloric acid (16 c.c.) was added drop by drop. It was then kept for 45 minutes allowing it to attain the room temperature. It was finally diluted with water, acidified with hydrochloric acid and the oil separating was taken up in ether and washed. On evaporation of the solvent a light yellow oily liquid was obtained which boiled at 170°/4 mm., yield 14.3 g. (Found: C, 61.4; H, 7.2. $C_{15}H_{22}O_4N_2$ requires C, 61.2; H, 7.4 per cent).

β -Methyl-n-hexane- $\alpha\beta\delta$ -tricarboxylic Acid (III, $R_1=Et$; $R_2=H$).—The above product (13.9 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 12 hours with concentrated hydrochloric acid (75 c.c.). The clear solution, thus obtained, was evaporated to dryness and the solid residue extracted with ether. The solid product obtained on evaporation of the ether after several crystallisations from concentrated hydrochloric acid melted at 173°. The *pure* acid is readily soluble in water and hot concentrated hydrochloric acid, but sparingly soluble in ether and insoluble in light petrol. (Found: C, 51.5; H, 6.9. $C_{10}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 51.7; H, 6.9 per cent).

The *triethyl ester* was prepared by heating the acid (10 g.) at 110° for 6 hours with absolute alcohol (30 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (3 c.c.) in a current of hot alcohol vapour. The product was then worked up and distilled in the usual way, b. p. 140°/5mm., yield 10.5 g. (Found: C, 60.6; H, 8.7. $C_{18}H_{28}O_6$ requires C, 60.7; H, 8.8 per cent).

Ethyl 3-methyl-5-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-2:3-dicarboxylate (V, $R_1=X=Et$; $R_2=CO_2Et$) was prepared by heating the triethyl ester (10.3 g.) on the water-bath with a fine suspension of sodium (0.92 g.) in benzene (25 c.c.). The reaction started on heating and was complete in $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. The product was treated with ice-water and acidified with ice-cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The benzene layer was separated, washed well with water and the benzene evaporated. The residual oil distilled at 130°/5mm., yield 6.5 g. It gives a violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 8.1. $C_{14}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 62.2; H, 8.1 per cent).

3-Methyl-5-ethylcyclopentan-1-one-3-carboxylic Acid (V , $R_1 = Et$; $R_2 = X = H$).—The above product (6.2 g.) was heated on a sand-bath for 10 hours with 6% hydrochloric acid (70 c.c.). The product was neutralised with sodium carbonate and extracted with ether to remove any neutral matter. It was then acidified, saturated with salt and extracted with ether. The acid was obtained as a liquid on evaporation of the ether. The *semicarbazone* crystallises from methyl alcohol as colourless needles, m.p. 191° . (Found: C, 52.5; H, 7.4. $C_{15}H_{17}O_3N_2$ requires C, 52.8; H, 7.5 per cent).

The *ethyl ester* was prepared by heating the keto-acid with absolute alcohol in presence of hydrogen chloride. It is a colourless liquid, b. p. $110^\circ/8$ mm. The *semicarbazone* of the ethyl ester crystallises from dilute alcohol in colourless crystals, m.p., $142-43^\circ$. (Found: C, 56.2; H, 8.0. $C_{13}H_{15}O_2N_2$ requires C, 56.4; H, 8.2 per cent).

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